

A Modified Partial Hybrid Stress Finite Element Method for the Laminated Composite Plate Analysis

Chung-Yue Wang and Hsu-Kuang Ching

Department of Civil Engineering
National Central University, Chungli, 32054
Taiwan, R. O. C.

ABSTRACT

A new element – modified partial hybrid stress element – is presented for three-dimensional analysis of thick laminated composite plate. For this new element, displacement field (u, v, w) and transverse stress field ($\sigma_{yz}, \sigma_{xz}, \sigma_z$) are independently assumed in the functional modified from Hellinger-Ressiner variational principle. The assembled global stiffness matrix of laminated plate is obtained via variational method. Moreover, a twenty-node hexahedron element is employed in each layer for the displacement field and only interface traction continuity and traction free boundary conditions need be satisfied in the assumed transverse stress field. Equation of equilibrium and the constitutive relations of stress-strain will be automatically implied in the variational sense. Comparisons between the present results and available solutions demonstrate the accuracy and efficiency of this new element.

Keywords: Laminate, hybrid stress element, variational principle, interface continuity

1. INTRODUCTION

Structures made of composite materials are increasingly used in many branches of engineering from aerospace industry to building construction due to the advantages such as high strength- to weight and stiffness- to -weight ratios. The methods to find the response of composite laminates under various conditions have appeared to be of most concern in this field. The transverse stresses effect on the behavior of plate are more pronounced than that in isotropic plates due to the very large ratios of elastic modulus to shear modulus. Failure modes in such materials often consist of delamination and microcracks resulting from excessive interlaminar stresses. Thus, for better damage analysis, efficient analytical and numerical methods are necessary for accurate estimation the stress state of the laminate.

A number of different plate finite elements have proposed by many researchers [1–28]. Among those finite element methods, the hybrid stress FEM originated by Pian [6] is more attractive because its capability of getting accurate stress prediction. For the last decade, many researchers are continuously working on this topic for obtaining an efficient and accurate prediction of the behavior of composite structures [7-28]. In the conventional hybrid stress element methods, three displacement components and six stresses are considered within each layer. However, it is usually very time consuming because of the element matrix size and the operations involved in calculating the element stiffness. To overcome this drawback, Reissner [29, 30] suggested a mixed variational principle and was derived independently by Moriya [4] through Hu-Washizu principle. In both schemes transverse stresses and displacements are interpolated separately. Based on this modified variational principle, Pian and Li [20] developed a mixed form hybrid stress element. Jing and Liao [22] has applied Hellinger-

Reissner functional to propose a partial hybrid stress element method which just consider transverse shear stresses and three displacement components independently in the scheme. In the present paper, a new element—a modified partial hybrid stress element – based on the 9 variables ($\sigma_{xz}, \sigma_{yz}, \sigma_{zz}, u, v, w$) variational functional are proposed for the analysis of thick laminated composite plates. Different from Jing and Liao's partial hybrid stress element, this new element include the σ_{zz} into the formulation for better prediction of the transverse stress distribution. The twenty-node hexahedron element is employed in each layer for the delamination analysis in the future research. The interface traction continuity condition and traction-free boundary conditions are satisfied. The equation of equilibrium is enforced through variational sense. The accuracy of this modified partial hybrid stress element is demonstrated by comparing the results with existing elasticity solutions and other researcher's works.

2. MIXED FORM VARIATIONAL PRINCIPLE

The modified Hellinger–Reissner Principle [4, 22, 29, 30] which involves the displacements and only transverse stresses for an elastic body of volume V with prescribed traction boundary condition \bar{T} on S_σ is expressed in the form as

$$\Pi_{HR}^* = \sum_n^N \int_{V_n} \left[\frac{1}{2} ([D_p] \{U\})^T [C_p] ([D_p] \{U\}) + \{\sigma_t\}^T [C_{tp}] ([D_p] \{U\}) \right. \\ \left. - \frac{1}{2} \{\sigma_t\}^T [S_t^*] \{\sigma_t\} + \{\sigma_t\}^T ([D_t] \{U\}) \right] dV - \int_{S_\sigma} \{\bar{T}\}^T \{U\} dS \quad (1)$$

where we divided the stresses σ , the strain ϵ into the inplane and transverse parts,

$$\{\sigma_p\} = [\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_{xy}]^T \text{ and } \{\sigma_t\} = [\sigma_{yz}, \sigma_{xz}, \sigma_z]^T \quad (2)$$

$$\{\epsilon_p\} = [\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y, \gamma_{xy}]^T = [D_p] \{U\} \text{ and } \{\epsilon_t\} = [\gamma_{yz}, \gamma_{xz}, \epsilon_z]^T = [D_t] \{U\} \quad (3)$$

and those $\{\sigma_p\}, \{\sigma_t\}, \{\epsilon_p\}, \{\epsilon_t\}$ satisfy the stress-strain relations for general anisotropic elastic material as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \{\epsilon_p\} \\ \{\epsilon_t\} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_p & S_{pt} \\ S_{pt}^T & S_t \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \{\sigma_p\} \\ \{\sigma_t\} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{13} & S_{14} & S_{15} & S_{16} \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & S_{23} & S_{24} & S_{25} & S_{26} \\ S_{13} & S_{23} & S_{33} & S_{34} & S_{35} & S_{36} \\ S_{14} & S_{24} & S_{34} & S_{44} & S_{45} & S_{46} \\ S_{15} & S_{25} & S_{35} & S_{45} & S_{55} & S_{56} \\ S_{16} & S_{26} & S_{36} & S_{46} & S_{56} & S_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \{\sigma_p\} \\ \{\sigma_t\} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$[C_p] = [S_p]^{-1}, [C_{pt}] = -[C_p] [S_{pt}] = [C_{tp}]^T \quad (5)$$

$$[S_t^*] = [S_t] - [S_{pt}]^T [C_p] [S_{pt}] \quad (6)$$

3. MIXED FORMED HYBRID STRESS ELEMENT

The transverse stresses $\{\sigma_t\}$ and displacement $\{U\}$ are in terms of stress parameters $\{\beta\}$, and nodal displacements $\{q\}$, respectively, as

$$\{\sigma_t\} = [T_s][P] \{\beta\}, \quad \{U\} = [N]\{q\}$$

and consequently $\{\epsilon_p\} = [D_p]\{U\} = [B_p]\{q\}$, $\{\epsilon_t\} = [D_t]\{U\} = [B_t]\{q\}$ (7)

where $[P]$ and $[N]$ are assumed functions, $\{\beta\}$, are stress parameters, $[T_\sigma]$ is stress transformation matrix between global coordinates (x,y,z) and local natural coordinates (ξ,η,ζ) and $\{q\}$ are nodal displacements. Substituting Eqs. (7) into Eq. (1), and eliminating $\{\beta\}$ by applying the stationary condition with respect to $\{\beta\}$, we obtain the following relation between $\{\beta\}$ and $\{q\}$ as

$$\{\beta\} = [H]^{-1} [G] \{q\} \quad (8)$$

and the element stiffness matrix $[k] = [k_p] + [G]^T [H]^{-1} [G]$

where

$$[k_p] = \int_{V_n} [B_p]^T [C_p] [B_p] dV, \quad [G] = \int_{V_n} [P]^T [T_\sigma]^T ([C_{tp}] [B_p] + [B_t]) dV$$

and

$$[H] = \int_{V_n} [P]^T [T_\sigma]^T [S_t^*] [T_\sigma] [P] dV \quad (9)$$

4. ASSUMED TRANSVERSE STRESS FIELD

In order to make the approximation of the compatibility relation of transverse stresses more accurately, the assumed stress $[\sigma_t]$ in equation (7) should be consistent with the transverse strains $\{\epsilon_t\}$ derived from the displacement field $\{U\}$. For a twenty-node isoparametric hexahedron element, the displacement will contain the following 20 terms:

$$\{U\}: (1, \xi, \eta, \zeta; \xi^2, \eta^2, \zeta^2, \xi\eta, \eta\zeta, \xi\zeta; \xi^2\eta, \xi^2\zeta, \eta^2\xi, \eta^2\zeta, \zeta^2\xi, \zeta^2\eta, \xi\eta\zeta; \xi^2\eta\zeta, \eta^2\xi\zeta, \zeta^2\xi\eta).$$

The transverse stresses $[s_t]$ and strains $[e_t]$ should contain the following terms to match the constitutive relations:

$$[\sigma_t], [e_t]: (1, \xi, \eta, \xi^2, \eta^2, \xi\eta, \xi^2\eta, \xi\eta^2), \zeta (1, \xi, \eta, \xi^2, \eta^2, \xi\eta), \zeta^2 (1, \xi, \eta).$$

For a N-layer composite laminate, the interface and boundary conditions of traction are then imposed to established the relations of stress parameter vector $\{\beta^i\}$ of all the layers ($i = 1, N$). The obtained relations are employed in the layer assembly process to generate the assembled vector $\{\beta\}$. It can be derived that the total number of independent $\{\beta\}$ parameters of a N-layer laminate with traction free lower surface and shear traction free upper surface is $27N - 12$. Thus, compared with conventional hybrid stress finite element it has reduce numerous computational effort in the analysis for multilayered thick composite plate.

5. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

The performances of this element are verified by a few examples with exact solutions obtained by Pagano [31]. Simply supported square three-layer $[0/90/0]$ laminated plates are consider. Two different length-to-thickness ratios a/h are used in these examples. Each layer of the laminates is of equal thickness and the material constants with respect to its principal material axes (1,2,3) are specified by $E_{22}/E_{11} = E_{33}/E_{11} = 0.04$, $G_{12}/E_{11} = G_{13}/E_{11} = 0.02$, $G_{23}/E_{11} = 0.008$, $n_{12} = n_{13} = n_{23}$

= 0.25. The loading $q(x,y) = q_0 \sin(\pi x/a) \sin(\pi y/a)$ is applied on the top surface of the laminate in the examples. Through thickness distributions of normalized $\bar{\sigma}_{xy}, \bar{\sigma}_{xz}, \bar{\sigma}_{yz}, \bar{\sigma}_z$, at specific points are shown in Figures 1 to 4. These results are obtained from a 4x4 mesh in the $x - y$ plane and calculated directly at specific nodal points. Exact solutions and the results from classical lamination theory (CLT) are also given in these figures. From these figures it is observed that the present method can provide very accurate stresses predictions. Table 1 lists the results from different researchers dealing with the same problem. It can be seen from the table that the present method are comparable with those of conventional hybrid stress FEM.

Figure 1. In-plane shear stress distribution, $s = 4, \sigma_{xy}(0, 0, z/h)$.

Figure 2. Transverse shear stress distribution $s = 4, \sigma_{xz}(0, a/2, z/h)$.

Figure 3. Transverse shear stress distribution $s = 4, \sigma_{yz}(a/2, 0, z/h)$.

Figure 4. Transverse normal stress distribution $s = 4, \sigma_z = (a/2, a/2, z/h)$.

Table 1. Normalized stresses for $a=b, [0/90/0]$ laminate

S	SOURCE	S_{xx}	S_{yy}	S_{xy}	S_{yz}	S_{xz}	S_{zz}
4	Pagano [31]	0.8010 -0.7550	0.534 -0.556	-0.0511 0.0505	0.2170	0.256	0.250 0.
	Reddy [32]	0.7345	—	—	0.1832	—	—
	Liou & Sun [16]	0.717 -0.679	0.517 -0.541	-0.0476 0.0485	0.221	0.263	—
	Present	0.7432 -0.7068	0.5093 -0.5363	-0.0494 0.0492	0.2263	0.2632	0.2657 0.0

S	SOURCE	S_{xx}	S_{yy}	S_{xy}	S_{yz}	S_{xz}	S_{zz}
10	Pagano [31]	0.590 -0.590	0.285 -0.288	-0.0289 0.0289	0.1228	0.357	0.1 0.0
	Reddy [32]	0.5684	—	—	0.1033	—	—
	Liou & Sun [16]	0.580 -0.580	0.285 -0.289	-0.0283 0.0284	0.127	0.367	—
	Jing & Liao [22]	0.5884 -0.5879	0.2834 -0.2873	-0.0288 0.0290	0.1284	0.3627	0.1057 0.00596
	Moriya [4]	0.5759 -0.5785	0.2820 -0.2890	-0.0286 0.0288	0.1296	0.3993	—
	Present	0.5925 -0.5920	0.2854 -0.2894	-0.0290 0.0290	0.1345	0.3667	0.1033 0.0

$$S_{xx} = 1/qs^2 \sigma_{xx} (a/2, b/2, \pm h/2), S_{yy} = 1/qs^2 \sigma_{yy} (a/2, b/2, \pm h/6), S_{xy} = 1/qs^2 \sigma_{xy} (0, 0, \pm h/2)$$

$$S_{yz} = 1/qs^2 \sigma_{yz} (a/2, 0, 0), S_{xz} = 1/qs^2 \sigma_{xz} (0, b/2, 0), S_{zz} = 1/qs^2 \sigma_{zz} (a/2, b/2, \pm h/2)$$

6. CONCLUSION

The 3-D modified hybrid stress FEM is developed in this paper. Only transverse stress components needed to be assumed and the self-equilibrium stress field is not required. Advantages of this newly derived element are that the construction of assumed stress field is easier than conventional hybrid stress finite element [9,10,12,14,19,21] and continuity conditions at interfaces of layers for transverse stresses are exactly obtained. In addition, the computer time and storage space are reduced enormously. This new modified partial hybrid stress element can also be applied to the 3-dimensional stress analysis of layered general anisotropic medium. Finally, transverse normal stress σ_z is directly obtained from assumed stress field, so that the damage caused by delamination or the contact pressure between foreign object and plate can be analyzed reasonably in the analysis of laminated composite plates.

References

1. Pryor, C. W. Jr. and Barker, R. M., "A Finite Element Analysis Including Transverse Shear Effects for Application to Laminated Plates," AIAA Journal, Vol. 9, pp. 912 - 917, 1972.
2. Lee, James D., "Three Dimensional Finite Element Analysis of Layered Fiber-Reinforced Composite Materials," Computers & Structures Vol. 12, pp. 319 - 339, 1980.
3. Di Sciuva, Marco, "Development of an Anisotropic, Multilayered, Shear-Deformable Rectangular Plate Element," Computers and Structures, Vol. 21, No. 4, pp. 789 - 765, 1985.
4. Moriya, K., "Laminated Plate and Shell Elements for Finite Element Analysis of Advanced Fiber Reinforced Composite Structures," (in Japanese), Trans. Japan Soc. Mech. Eng. (Series A), 52, No. 478, pp. 1600 - 1607, 1986.
5. Di Sciuva, Marco, "An Improved Shear-Deformation Theory for Moderately Thick Multilayered Anisotropic Shells and Plates," Journal of Applied Mechanics, Sept. 1987, Vol. 54, pp. 589 - 596.
6. Pian, T. H. H., "Derivation of Element Stiffness Matrices by Assumed Stress Distributions," AIAA Journal, Vol. 2, No. 7, July 1964, pp. 1333 - 1336.
7. Tong, P. and Pian, T. H. H., "A Variational Principle and the Convergence of a Finite Element Method Based on Assumed Stress Distribution," International Journal of Solids and Structures, Vol. 5, No. 5, May 1969, pp. 463 - 472.
8. Mau, S. T., Tong, P. and Pian, T. H. H., "Finite Element Solutions for Laminated Thick Plates," J. Composite Materials, Vol. 6 (April 1972), pp. 304 - 311.
9. Spilker, R. L., Chou, S. C. and Orringer, O., "Alternate Hybrid-Stress Elements for Analysis of Multilayer Composite Plates," J. Composite Materials, Vol. 11 (January 1977), pp. 51 - 70.

10. Nishioka, T. and Atluri, S. N., "Assumed Stress Finite Element Analysis of Through-Cracks in Angle-Ply Laminates," AIAA Journal Vol. 18, No. 9, September 1980, pp. 1125 - 1132.
11. Pian, T. H. H. and Chen, Da-Peng, "Alternative Ways for Formulation of Hybrid Stress Elements," International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering, Vol. 18, pp. 1679 - 1684 (1982).
12. Spilker, R. L., "Hybrid-Stress Eight-Node Element for Thin and Thick Multilayer Laminated Plates," International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering, Vol. 18, 801 - 828 (1982).
13. Pian, T. H. H., Chen, Da-Peng and Kang, David, "A New Formulation of Hybrid/Mixed Finite Element," Computers & Structures Vol. 16, No. 1, pp. 81 - 87, 1983.
14. Wang, Cheng, "Assumed Stress Hybrid 3-D Multilayer Element," Progress Report, National Center for Composite Materials Research, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, August 5, 1987.
15. Wang, S. S., "Three Dimensional Hybrid-Stress Finite Element Analysis of Composite Laminates with Cracks and Cutouts," Pressure Vessel Design and Analysis, Vol. 98-2, 1987, pp. 235 - 246.
16. Liou, Wen-Jinn and Sun, C. T., "A Three-Dimensional Hybrid Stress Isoparametric Element for the Analysis of Laminated Composite Plates," Computers & Structures, Vol. 25, No. 2, pp. 241-249, 1987.
17. Chen, Wanji and Cheung, Y. K., "A New Approach for the Hybrid Element Method," International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering, Vol. 24, pp. 1697 - 1709 (1987).
18. Pian, Theodore H. H. and Chang-Chun Wu, "A Rational Approach for Choosing Stress Terms for Hybrid Finite Element Formulation," International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering, Vol. 26, pp. 2331 - 2343 (1988).
19. Sun, C. T. and Li, Suian, "Three-Dimensional Effective Elastic Constants for Thick Laminates," Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 22, pp. 629 - 639, July 1988.
20. Pian, Theodore H. H. and Li, Mingsang, "Stress Analysis of Laminated Composites by Hybrid Finite Elements," Discretization Methods in Structural Mechanics, IUTAM/IACM Symposium, Vienna, Austria, 1989, Kuhn, G. and Mang, H. (Eds.), pp. 363 - 372.
21. Chen, Wen-Hwa and Huang, Tain-Fu, "Three Dimensional Interlaminar Stress Analysis at Free Edges of Composite Laminate," Computers & Structures Vol. 32, No. 6, pp. 1275- 1286, 1989.
22. Jing, Hung-Syng and Liao, Ming-Liang, "Partial Hybrid Stress Element for the Analysis of Thick Laminated Composite Plates," International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering, Vol. 28, pp. 2831 - 2827 (1989).
23. Li, M. S., "Higher Order Laminated Composite Plate Analysis by Hybrid Finite Element Method," Ph. D. Thesis, Mass. Inst. of Tech., 1989.
24. Kang, D. S., "Present Finite Element Technology from a Hybrid Formulation Perspective," Computers & Structures Vol. 35, No. 4, pp. 321 - 327, 1990.
25. Cheung, Y. K. and Chen, W., "Generalized Hybrid Degenerated Elements for Plates and Shells," Computers & Structures, Vol. 36, No. 2, pp. 279 - 290, 1990.
26. Wilt, T. E., Saleeb, A. F. and Chang, T. Y., "A Mixed Element for Laminated Plates and Shells," Computers & Structures, Vol. 37, No. 4, pp. 597- 611, 1990.
27. Wang, Cheng-Chi and Chen, Rong-Sheng, "Analysis of Stress Concentration in Composite Laminates with a Hole Using the Partial Hybrid Stress Element Method," Journal of the Chinese Institute of Civil and Hydraulic Engineering, Vol. 2, No. 4, pp. 337-345 (1990).
28. Jing, H.-S. and Liao, M.-L., "Three Dimensional Global-Local Analysis of Thick Composite Laminates with Partial Hybrid Stress Sublaminates," private communication.
29. Reissner, E., "On a Certain Mixed Variational Theorem and a Proposed Application," Int. J. Num. Meth. Engng. 20, pp. 1366 -1368, 1984.
30. Reissner, E., "On a Mixed Variational Theorem and on Shear Deformable Plate Theory," Int. J. Num. Meth. Engng. 23, pp. 193 -198, 1986.
31. Pagano, N. J. "Exact Solutions for Rectangular Bidirectional Composites and Sandwich Plates," J. Composite Materials, Vol. 4 (January 1970), pp. 20- 34.
32. Reddy, J. N., "A Simple Higher - Order Theory for Laminated Composite Plates," J. Appl. Mech. , Vol. 51, pp. 745 - 752, 1984.